

Investigation on viscous antagonism of ternary liquid mixtures and its relation to concentration

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The densities and viscosities of ternary mixtures of tetrahydrofuran + methanol + benzene and isopropanol + benzene + *n*-hexane have been measured at 303.15, 313.15 and 323.15 K over the entire composition range. The data have been analyzed using the equation developed by Kaletune-Gencer and Peleg. The experimental results have been discussed and explained in terms of molecular package and electrostriction.

Tetrahydrofuran (THF) is a good industrial solvent. It figures prominently in the high energy battery industry and has found its application in organic syntheses as manifested from the physico-chemical studies in this medium^{1,2}. Alcohols are very widely used in industry, including the manufacture of pharmaceuticals and cosmetic products, in enology and as an energy source. Rheology is the branch of science that studies material deformation and flow, and is increasingly applied to analyze the viscous behaviour of many pharmaceutical products³⁻¹¹ and to establish their stability and even bioavailability – since it has been firmly established that viscosity influences drug absorption rate in the body^{12,13}.

The present investigation quantifies the viscous antagonism established in two ternary mixtures studied here at different temperatures. Since these systems exhibit volume contraction, an analysis has also been made of the density of the mixtures at various temperatures.

Results and discussion

The study of the viscous behavior of pharmaceuticals, foodstuffs, cosmetics or industrial products, etc., is essential for confirming that their viscosity is appropriate for the contemplated use of the products. Viscous antagonism is defined as the interaction between the components of a system causing the net viscosity of the latter to be less than the sum of the viscosities of each component considered separately. In contraposition to viscous antagonism, viscous synergy is the term used in application to the interaction between the components of a system that causes the total viscosity of the latter to be greater than the sum of the viscosities of each component considered separately. In turn, if the total viscosity of the sys-

tem is equal to the sum of the viscosities of each component considered separately, the system is said to lack interaction^{14,15}.

The method most widely used to analyze the antagonistic and synergic behaviour of various solvent-mixtures is that developed by Kaletune-Gencer and Peleg¹⁶ allowing quantification of the antagonistic interactions taking place in mixtures involving variable proportions of the constituent components. The method compares the viscosity of the system, determined experimentally, η_{exp} , with the viscosity expected in the absence of interaction, η_{mix} , defined as¹⁷,

$$\eta_{\text{mix}} = \sum_i^n X_i \eta_i \quad (1)$$

where X_i , and η_i are the fraction by weight and viscosity measured experimentally, of the *i*-th component respectively.

This procedure is used when Newtonian fluids are involved, since in non-Newtonian systems shear rate must be taken into account, and other antagonism indices are defined in consequence¹⁸.

In order to secure more comparable viscous antagonism results, the so-called antagonistic index (I_η), introduced by Howell¹⁹, is also taken into account,

$$I_\eta = (\eta_{\text{mix}} - \eta_{\text{exp}})/\eta_{\text{mix}} = \Delta\eta/\eta_{\text{mix}} \quad (2)$$

The method used to analyze volume contraction and dilatation is similar to that applied to viscosity. i.e. density of the mixture is determined experimentally, ρ_{exp} and a calculation is made of its theoretical value ρ_{mix} , in the

supposition that volume contraction exists, based on the following expression¹⁷,

$$\rho_{\text{mix}} = \sum_i^n X_i \rho_i \quad (3)$$

where ρ_i denotes the density, measured experimentally of i -th component. Accordingly, when $\rho_{\text{exp}} > \rho_{\text{mix}}$, volume contraction occurs.

The physical properties of various pure solvents (tetrahydrofuran, isopropanol, methanol, benzene and n -hexane) along with their literature values at various temperatures are recorded in Table 1.

The measurements made yielded the viscosity values determined experimentally, ρ_{exp} and the viscosity values expected in the absence of interaction, η_{mix} along with antagonistic interaction index (I_η) of various ternary liquid mixtures studied here at different temperatures are recorded in Table 2. From Table 2 in case of mixture tetrahydrofuran + methanol + benzene it is observed that the antagonistic interaction in the mixture is maximum where maximum amount of benzene (80 mass%) is present in the mixture whereas it is minimum where the mixture does not contain benzene for all temperatures studied here. The explanation of this behaviour is based on the known phenomenon of molecular dissociation, as a consequence of weakening the hydrogen bonds formed between the

Table 1. Physical properties of various pure solvents at different temperatures

T/K	Tetrahydrofuran (THF)		Isopropanol		Methanol		Benzene		n -Hexane	
	This work	Lit.	This work	Lit.	This work	Lit.	This work	Lit.	This work	Lit.
					$\rho_0/\text{g cm}^{-3}$					
303.15	0.8757	0.8734 ^a	0.7854	0.7766 ^b	0.7846	0.7846 ^a	0.8637	0.8682 ^c	0.6497	0.6529 ^e
313.15	0.8673	0.8661 ^a	0.7704	0.7681 ^b	0.7772	0.7772 ^a	0.8604	0.8574 ^d	0.6428	0.6435 ^e
323.15	0.8583	0.8582 ^a	0.7651	-	0.7675	0.7675 ^a	0.8517	0.8466 ^c	0.6332	0.6341 ^e
					η_0/cp					
303.15	0.4452	0.4451 ^a	1.7686	1.792 ^b	0.4086	0.4089 ^a	0.5637	0.5612 ^c	0.2643	0.2774 ^e
313.15	0.4088	0.4088 ^a	1.3611	1.352 ^b	0.3847	0.3848 ^a	0.5029	0.5000 ^d	0.2487	0.2504 ^e
323.15	0.3716	0.3745 ^a	1.2713	-	0.3308	0.3311 ^a	0.4381	0.4362 ^c	0.2307	0.2333 ^e

^aRef. = 24, ^bRef. = 25, ^cRef. = 26, ^dRef. = 27, ^eRef. = 28.

Table 2. Viscosities of the ternary liquid mixtures without interaction (η_{mix}) and with interaction (η_{exp}) with antagonistic interaction index (I_η) at various temperatures

(1) Tetrahydrofuran (THF) + methanol (MeOH) + benzene (C ₆ H ₆)											
Mass% of THF	Mass% of MeOH	Mass% of C ₆ H ₆	η_{mix}			$\eta_{\text{exp}}/\text{cp}$			I_η		
			303.15 K	313.15 K	323.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	323.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	323.15 K
			0.5363	0.4817	0.4207	0.4190	0.3962	0.3710	0.2188	0.1774	0.1182
10	10	80	0.5167	0.4663	0.4087	0.4517	0.4213	0.3748	0.1259	0.0966	0.0829
20	15	65	0.4816	0.4392	0.3859	0.4060	0.3839	0.3674	0.1570	0.1259	0.0481
30	30	40	0.4679	0.4286	0.3773	0.4629	0.3823	0.3713	0.0108	0.1080	0.0158
35	35	30	0.4543	0.4180	0.3686	0.3981	0.3972	0.3659	0.1236	0.0497	0.0073
40	40	20	0.4406	0.4074	0.3598	0.4337	0.3825	0.3618	0.0156	0.0610	-0.0053
45	45	10	0.4269	0.3967	0.3512	0.4482	0.4075	0.4297	-0.0498	-0.0271	-0.2235
50	50	00	0.4365	0.4039	0.3586	0.3897	0.3777	0.3801	0.1072	0.0648	-0.0599
55	40	05	0.4461	0.4109	0.3660	0.4063	0.3719	0.4296	0.0892	0.0951	-0.1737
60	30	10	0.4556	0.4181	0.3734	0.3882	0.3659	0.3685	0.1480	0.1248	0.0132
65	20	15	0.4652	0.4252	0.3808	0.4456	0.3789	0.3713	0.0422	0.1089	0.0249
70	10	20	0.4748	0.4323	0.3882	0.4050	0.3996	0.4009	0.1470	0.0757	-0.0326
75	00	25	0.4689	0.4276	0.3849	0.3954	0.3811	0.4007	0.1567	0.1088	-0.0410
80	00	20	0.4570	0.4182	0.3782	0.3948	0.3760	0.3863	0.1362	0.1009	-0.0213
90	00	10									

(2) Isopropanol (Me₂CHOH) + *n*-hexane (C₆H₁₄) + benzene (C₆H₆)

Mass % of Me ₂ CHOH	Mass % of C ₆ H ₁₄	Mass % of C ₆ H ₆									
00	65	35	0.3691	0.3377	0.3033	1.1240	0.4077	0.3936	-2.0453	-0.2074	-0.2978
05	80	15	0.3844	0.3424	0.3138	0.3808	0.3207	0.2600	0.0094	0.0635	0.1715
10	10	80	0.6542	0.5633	0.5007	0.4413	0.4126	0.4092	0.3255	0.2675	0.1827
20	15	65	0.7598	0.6364	0.5736	0.4682	0.4354	0.4118	0.3838	0.3158	0.2821
30	25	45	0.8503	0.6968	0.6362	0.5654	0.5082	0.4632	0.3351	0.2707	0.2719
40	35	25	0.9409	0.7572	0.6988	0.6739	0.6475	0.5600	0.2837	0.1449	0.1986
50	45	05	1.0314	0.8176	0.7614	0.7315	0.6858	0.6509	0.2908	0.1612	0.1451
60	40	00	1.1669	0.9161	0.8551	0.9803	0.6940	0.6526	0.1599	0.2425	0.2368
70	20	10	1.3472	1.0528	0.9799	0.9100	0.6983	0.6239	0.3245	0.3367	0.3633
80	00	20	1.5276	1.1895	1.1046	1.0656	0.8413	0.7631	0.3024	0.2927	0.3092
90	05	05	1.6331	1.2626	1.1776	0.9609	0.8137	0.7238	0.4116	0.3555	0.3854

molecules of the components of the mixture due to presence of benzene – producing a decrease in size of the molecular package which logically implies an increase in antagonistic interaction index (I_{η}). Some result was reported earlier¹⁷ in the density and viscosity measurements of the ternary mixtures. Further Table 2 in case of mixture isopropanol + *n*-hexane + benzene shows that the value of antagonistic interaction index (I_{η}) is maximum when maximum amount of isopropanol is present in the mixture and it is minimum when the mixture contains no isopropanol. The possible explanation of this behaviour is that the maximum addition of isopropanol to the mixture either destroys or complicates the establishment of molecular

interaction formed between the molecules of the components of the mixture resulting a maximum value of antagonistic interaction index (I_{η}).

The density of the mixture is determined experimentally, ρ_{exp} and a calculation is made of theoretical value, ρ_{mix} for two ternary liquid mixtures at 303.15, 313.15 and 323.15 K are presented in Table 3. A perusal of Table 3 shows that the values of density determined experimentally, ρ_{exp} for both mixtures for various mass% and various temperatures are higher than those of its theoretical values, ρ_{mix} in the supposition that volume contraction exists, based on the eq. (3). This type of behaviour

Table 3. Densities of the ternary liquid mixtures calculated theoretically (ρ_{mix}) and determined experimentally (ρ_{exp}) at various temperatures(1) Tetrahydrofuran (THF) + methanol (MeOH) + benzene (C₆H₆)

Mass % of THF	Mass % of MeOH	Mass % of C ₆ H ₆	$\rho_{\text{mix}}/\text{g cm}^{-3}$			$\rho_{\text{exp}}/\text{g cm}^{-3}$		
			303.15 K	313.15 K	323.15 K	303.15 K	313.15 K	323.15 K
10	10	80	0.8569	0.8528	0.8439	0.8599	0.8545	0.8496
20	15	65	0.8542	0.8493	0.8404	0.8570	0.8523	0.8459
30	30	40	0.8436	0.8375	0.8284	0.8452	0.8404	0.8349
35	35	30	0.8402	0.8337	0.8245	0.8415	0.8361	0.8296
40	40	20	0.8367	0.8299	0.8207	0.8390	0.8336	0.8257
45	45	10	0.8335	0.8261	0.8168	0.8352	0.8310	0.8230
50	50	00	0.8301	0.8222	0.8129	0.8306	0.8263	0.8166
55	40	05	0.8387	0.8309	0.8216	0.8375	0.8353	0.8269
60	30	10	0.8472	0.8396	0.8304	0.8491	0.8397	0.8345
65	20	15	0.8557	0.8482	0.8391	0.8576	0.8504	0.8430
70	10	20	0.8642	0.8569	0.8479	0.8658	0.8610	0.8527
75	00	25	0.8727	0.8656	0.8566	0.8752	0.8670	0.8634
80	00	20	0.8733	0.8659	0.8569	0.8743	0.8667	0.8596
90	00	10	0.8745	0.8666	0.8576	0.8743	0.8664	0.8607

(2) Isopropanol (Me₂CHOH) + *n*-hexane (C₆H₁₄) + benzene (C₆H₆)

Mass% of Me ₂ CHOH	Mass% of C ₆ H ₁₄	Mass % of C ₆ H ₆							
00	65	35	0.7246	0.7190	0.7097	0.8798	0.8715	0.8686	
05	80	15	0.6886	0.6818	0.6726	0.8950	0.8843	0.8813	
10	10	80	0.8345	0.8296	0.8212	0.8585	0.8494	0.8430	
20	15	65	0.8159	0.8098	0.8016	0.8517	0.8437	0.8390	
30	25	45	0.7867	0.7790	0.7711	0.8552	0.8488	0.8427	
40	35	25	0.7575	0.7482	0.7406	0.8637	0.8543	0.8496	
50	45	05	0.7282	0.7175	0.7101	0.8688	0.8584	0.8556	
60	40	00	0.7311	0.7194	0.7123	0.8565	0.8460	0.8397	
70	20	10	0.7661	0.7539	0.7474	0.8257	0.8164	0.8114	
80	00	20	0.8011	0.7884	0.7824	0.8128	0.8029	0.7988	
90	05	05	0.7825	0.7685	0.7628	0.7946	0.7847	0.7408	

can be explained on the basis of known phenomenon of electrostriction as a consequence solvent molecules are accommodated in the void space left in the packing of dispersed solvent molecules. Same results are reported for 2 : 2 electrolytes in aqueous mixtures of THF²⁰.

Experimental

Tetrahydrofuran, methanol, isopropanol, *n*-hexane and benzene were purified as described earlier²¹. The values of densities and viscosities of these solvents at various temperatures are in good agreement with the literature data²⁴⁻²⁸.

Various mixtures of solutions with w/w concentrations of 0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 35, 40, 45, 50, 55, 60, 65, 70, 75, 80, 90 and 100% were prepared at 303.15, 313.15 and 323.15 K. Each solution thus prepared was distributed into three recipients to perform all the measurements in triplicate, with the aim of determining possible dispersion of the results obtained. The ternary liquid solutions were made by mass.

The densities (ρ) were measured with an Ostwald-Sperngel type pycnometer having a bulb volume of 25 cm³ and an internal diameter of the capillary of about 0.1 cm. The pycnometer was calibrated at 303.15, 313.15 and 323.15 K with doubly distilled water and benzene. The pycnometer with the test solution was equilibrated in a water bath maintained at ± 0.01 K of the desired temperatures by means of a mercury in glass thermoregulator and the temperature was determined with a calibrated thermometer and a Muller bridge. The pycnometer was then removed from the thermostatic bath, properly dried and weighed in an electronic balance. The balance used

here is Mettler Toledo AG-285, made in Switzerland. The evaporation losses remained insignificant during the time of actual measurements. Averages of triplicate measurements were taken into account. The density values were reproducible to $\pm 3 \times 10^{-5}$ g cm⁻³. Details have been described earlier²².

The viscosity of these mixtures was determined by means of a suspended-level Ubbelohde²³ viscometer at the desired temperatures (303.15, 313.15 and 323.15 K). The precision of the viscosity measurements were 0.05%. Details have been described earlier²¹.

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